

Keywords:

#tool, #policy, #legal, #RDM,
#researchdatamanagement, #FAIR, #EOSCinPractice

Supporting data trustworthiness using a repository policy generation tool

An EOSC in Practice Story of the Repository Policy Generator for data curators to manage repositories.

The project involved

NI4OS-Europe (National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe) is a European Horizon 2020 project funded under Grant Agreement no 857645. The project aims to be a core contributor to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) service portfolio, commit to EOSC governance and ensure inclusiveness on the European level for enabling global Open Science. It focuses on supporting the development and inclusion of the national Open Science Cloud initiatives in 15 Member States and Associated Countries in the EOSC governance.

"In order to create this tool we have collected the best practice policies for repositories. This is a step by step wizard that allows to easily create a policy for your repository, increasing its trustworthiness"

Eleni Toli, NI4OS-Europe Project Director, ATHENA RC

The Challenge

While collecting data for the NI4OS-Europe landscape survey, it was possible to observe that a significant number of repositories from the partner countries were not registered with [OpenDOAR](#) and other registries and aggregators. The number of those lacking clear repository policies, not providing interoperability or addressing the policies incorrectly, was even greater. To be considered trustworthy, a repository should have a transparent policy, informing users about the roles, responsibilities, rights and procedures aimed at ensuring that deposited data are preserved and disseminated in line with the FAIR principles. Policies are also required in the process of onboarding platforms and services into NI4OS-Europe, OpenAIRE and EOSC.

The solution

The **Repository Policy Generator (RePol)** is an open-source web application developed by the University of Belgrade that facilitates the process of drafting repository policies. In **RePol**, policy documents are generated by filling out a web form: inputs and choices made by users trigger predefined sections of text and clauses to be added to the output document, which can be downloaded in a machine-readable format and edited. RePol's source code is available on [GitHub](#). The tool can be used also to create not only repository policies but also more general policies and privacy policies.

The Users

This EOSC in practice story is mainly addressed to **repository managers, librarians or researchers, especially at smaller research institutions**, that lack information on policies for repository access and management. Having correct policies is important to guarantee the trustworthiness of repositories.

The service provider

RePol – Repository Policy Generator was developed by the [University of Belgrade Computer Centre \(RCUB\)](#). RCUB is a computer centre whose primary function is to provide computer and information-communication services to faculties and other institutions members of the University of Belgrade. Besides that, RCUB represents a central communication node of the Academic network of Serbia (AMRES). The University of Belgrade is one of NI4OS-Europe's partners.

Branko Marović, NI4OS-Europe WP4 Leader, University of Belgrade

Why do I need EOSC?

Providing this tool on the EOSC portal allows to:

- » Gain visibility at the European level
- » Reach a wider audience
- » Collect more feedback

The users benefit from an easy-to-use tool and do not need previous knowledge or legal background to access the resource

RePol is available on [NI4OS-Europe service catalogue](#), a regional catalogue through which all the project's services are onboarded to EOSC

What the users of the service say

"We used RePol to update the policies of our institutional repository. It is a very easy-to-use tool that guides you through the whole process. We were happy to see that it didn't require legal knowledge to address even privacy-related policies" Researcher, University of Cyprus

The impact on society

While not directly linked to society as a whole, the purposes of this tool are in line with the open access movement. The policy generator facilitates access to information that maybe would not be possible or would not be so easy to find and access, and in this sense promotes open science principles. It helps providers in regulating the important aspects of service management. The publication of policies increases the transparency of the services and the users' awareness of openness and privacy protection concerns thus contributing to the development of a service-based economy.

Across disciplines

Cross-disciplinarity is directly addressed in this story because the tool offers policy options that are not domain specific nor attached to a specific discipline and can be used in many different fields or applied to cross-disciplinary repositories.

Future developments

As for the other NI4OS tools, **RePol** will be continuously updated and improved also thanks to its open-source code.

Sustainability for an EOSC in practice

NI4Os-Europe's aspiration is that this resource and the others being developed by the project will be available after the project's end. Key to the sustainability of RePol is that NI4OS-Europe offers all its tools as open source solutions available through GitHub so that they can be taken up by the communities that are interested in using and further developing the tools.

Future funding model scenarios

The future sustainability plan including possible funding model scenarios and actions will be developed in the coming months as the project approaches its end and will be released at the beginning of 2023.

Useful material related to this story

- » [Presenting RePol](#)
- » [RePol Source code](#)

Want to learn more about the other services being developed by **NI4OS-Europe**? [Read here](#)

Liked this **#EOSCinPractice** story? Follow [@EOSCFuture](#) for more!

